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New Ideas On Super Stable By Hyper Stalk Of Stable-Cut In Cancer's Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph

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1 ABSTRACT

In this scientific research, (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut). Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a Stable-Cut pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut if the following expression is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut criteria holds

E' is Stable;

Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut if the following expression is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut criteria holds

E' is Stable;

and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$; Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut if the following expression is called Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut criteria holds

V' is Stable;

Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut if the following expression is called Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut criteria holds

V' is Stable;

and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$; Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable-Cut). Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called an Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut; a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic

v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut; an Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient; an Extreme V-SuperHyperStable-Cut if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut; a Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperStable-Cut if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut; an Extreme V-SuperHyperStable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the

Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient. In this scientific research, new setting is introduced for new SuperHyperNotions, namely, a SuperHyperStable-Cut and Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut. Two different types of SuperHyperDefinitions are debut for them but the research goes further and the SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperUniform, and SuperHyperClass based on that are well-defined and well-reviewed. The literature review is implemented in the whole of this research. For shining the elegance and the significancy of this research, the comparison between this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are featured. The definitions are followed by the examples and the instances thus the clarifications are driven with different tools. The applications are figured out to make sense about the theoretical aspect of this ongoing research. The “Cancer’s Recognition” are the under research to figure out the challenges make sense about ongoing and upcoming research. The special case is up. The cells are viewed in the deemed ways. There are different types of them. Some of them are individuals and some of them are well-modeled by the group of cells. These types are all officially called “SuperHyperVertex” but the relations amid them all officially called “SuperHyperEdge”. The frameworks “SuperHyperGraph” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” are chosen and elected to research about “Cancer’s Recognition”. Thus these complex and dense SuperHyperModels open up some avenues to research on theoretical segments and “Cancer’s Recognition”. Some avenues are posed to pursue this research. It’s also officially collected in the form of some questions and some problems. Assume a SuperHyperGraph. Assume a SuperHyperGraph. Then δ -SuperHyperStable-Cut is a maximal of SuperHyperVertices with a maximum cardinality such that either of the following expressions hold for the (Neutrosophic) cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$: there are $|S \cap N(s)| > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta$; and $|S \cap N(s)| < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta$. The first Expression, holds if S is an δ -SuperHyperOffensive. And the second Expression, holds if S is an δ -SuperHyperDefensive; a Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperStable-Cut is a maximal Neutrosophic of SuperHyperVertices with maximum Neutrosophic cardinality such that either of the following expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$ there are: $|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta$; and $|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta$. The first Expression, holds if S is a Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperOffensive. And the second Expression, holds if S is a Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperDefensive. It’s useful to define a “Neutrosophic” version of a SuperHyperStable-Cut. Since there’s more ways to get type-results to make a SuperHyperStable-Cut more understandable. For the sake of having Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, there’s a need to “redefine” the notion of a “SuperHyperStable-Cut”. The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there’s the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values. Assume a SuperHyperStable-Cut. It’s redefined a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut if the mentioned Table holds, concerning, “The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” with the key points, “The Values of The Vertices & The Number of Position in Alphabet”, “The Values of The SuperVertices&The maximum Values of Its Vertices”, “The Values of The Edges&The maximum Values of Its Vertices”, “The Values of The HyperEdges&The maximum Values of Its Vertices”, “The Values of The SuperHyperEdges&The maximum Values of Its Endpoints”. To get structural examples and instances, I’m

going to introduce the next SuperHyperClass of SuperHyperGraph based on a SuperHyperStable-Cut . It's the main. It'll be disciplinary to have the foundation of previous definition in the kind of SuperHyperClass. If there's a need to have all SuperHyperStable-Cut until the SuperHyperStable-Cut, then it's officially called a "SuperHyperStable-Cut" but otherwise, it isn't a SuperHyperStable-Cut . There are some instances about the clarifications for the main definition titled a "SuperHyperStable-Cut" . These two examples get more scrutiny and discernment since there are characterized in the disciplinary ways of the SuperHyperClass based on a SuperHyperStable-Cut . For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, there's a need to "redefine" the notion of a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut" and a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut" . The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's redefined "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph" if the intended Table holds. And a SuperHyperStable-Cut are redefined to a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut" if the intended Table holds. It's useful to define "Neutrosophic" version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut more understandable. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses if the intended Table holds. Thus SuperHyperPath, SuperHyperStable-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are "Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite", and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel" if the intended Table holds. A SuperHyperGraph has a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut" where it's the strongest [the maximum Neutrosophic value from all the SuperHyperStable-Cut amid the maximum value amid all SuperHyperVertices from a SuperHyperStable-Cut .] SuperHyperStable-Cut . A graph is a SuperHyperUniform if it's a SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as follows. It's SuperHyperPath if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions; it's SuperHyperStable-Cut if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges; it's SuperHyperStar it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges; it's SuperHyperBipartite it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; it's SuperHyperMultiPartite it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; it's a SuperHyperWheel if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex. The SuperHyperModel proposes the specific designs and the specific architectures. The SuperHyperModel is officially called "SuperHyperGraph" and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph". In this SuperHyperModel, The "specific" cells and "specific group" of cells are SuperHyperModeled as "SuperHyperVertices" and the common and intended properties between "specific" cells and "specific group" of cells are SuperHyperModeled as "SuperHyperEdges". Sometimes, it's useful to have some degrees of determinacy, indeterminacy, and neutrality to have more precise SuperHyperModel which in this case the SuperHyperModel is called "Neutrosophic". In the future research, the foundation will be based on the "Cancer's Recognition" and the results and the definitions will be introduced in redeemed ways. The recognition of the cancer in the long-term function. The specific region has been assigned by the model [it's called SuperHyperGraph] and the long cycle of the move from the cancer is

identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done. There are some specific models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some SuperHyperGeneral SuperHyperModels. The moves and the traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStable-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the longest SuperHyperStable-Cut or the strongest SuperHyperStable-Cut in those Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. For the longest SuperHyperStable-Cut, called SuperHyperStable-Cut, and the strongest SuperHyperStable-Cut, called Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, some general results are introduced. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges but it's not enough since it's essential to have at least three SuperHyperEdges to form any style of a SuperHyperStable-Cut. There isn't any formation of any SuperHyperStable-Cut but literarily, it's the deformation of any SuperHyperStable-Cut. It, literarily, deforms and it doesn't form. A basic familiarity with Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut theory, SuperHyperGraphs, and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs theory are proposed.

Keywords: Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, SuperHyperStable-Cut, Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition

AMS Subject Classification: 05C17, 05C22, 05E45

2 Applied Notions Under The Scrutiny Of The Motivation Of This Scientific Research

In this scientific research, there are some ideas in the featured frameworks of motivations. I try to bring the motivations in the narrative ways. Some cells have been faced with some attacks from the situation which is caused by the cancer's attacks. In this case, there are some embedded analysis on the ongoing situations which in that, the cells could be labelled as some groups and some groups or individuals have excessive labels which all are raised from the behaviors to overcome the cancer's attacks. In the embedded situations, the individuals of cells and the groups of cells could be considered as "new groups". Thus it motivates us to find the proper SuperHyperModels for getting more proper analysis on this messy story. I've found the SuperHyperModels which are officially called "SuperHyperGraphs" and "Extreme SuperHyperGraphs". In this SuperHyperModel, the cells and the groups of cells are defined as "SuperHyperVertices" and the relations between the individuals of cells and the groups of cells are defined as "SuperHyperEdges". Thus it's another motivation for us to do research on this SuperHyperModel based on the "Cancer's Recognition". Sometimes, the situations get worst. The situation is passed from the certainty and precise style. Thus it's the beyond them. There are three descriptions, namely, the degrees of determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality, for any object based on vague forms, namely, incomplete data, imprecise data, and uncertain analysis. The latter model could be considered on the previous SuperHyperModel. It's SuperHyperModel. It's SuperHyperGraph but it's officially called "Extreme SuperHyperGraphs". The cancer is the disease but the model is going to figure out what's going on this phenomenon. The special case of this disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The recognition of the cancer could help to find some treatments for

this disease. The SuperHyperGraph and Extreme SuperHyperGraph are the SuperHyperModels on the “Cancer’s Recognition” and both bases are the background of this research. Sometimes the cancer has been happened on the region, full of cells, groups of cells and embedded styles. In this segment, the SuperHyperModel proposes some SuperHyperNotions based on the connectivities of the moves of the cancer in the forms of alliances’ styles with the formation of the design and the architecture are formally called “ SuperHyperStable-Cut” in the themes of jargons and buzzwords. The prefix “SuperHyper” refers to the theme of the embedded styles to figure out the background for the SuperHyperNotions. The recognition of the cancer in the long-term function. The specific region has been assigned by the model [it’s called SuperHyperGraph] and the long cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn’t be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it’s said to be Extreme SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what’s happened and what’s done. There are some specific models, which are well-known and they’ve got the names, and some general models. The moves and the traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Extreme SuperHyperPath (-/SuperHyperStable-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the optimal SuperHyperStable-Cut or the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in those Extreme SuperHyperModels. Some general results are introduced. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible Extreme SuperHyperPath s have only two SuperHyperEdges but it’s not enough since it’s essential to have at least three SuperHyperEdges to form any style of a SuperHyperStable-Cut. There isn’t any formation of any SuperHyperStable-Cut but literarily, it’s the deformation of any SuperHyperStable-Cut. It, literarily, deforms and it doesn’t form.

Question 2.1. *How to define the SuperHyperNotions and to do research on them to find the “ amount of SuperHyperStable-Cut” of either individual of cells or the groups of cells based on the fixed cell or the fixed group of cells, extensively, the “amount of SuperHyperStable-Cut” based on the fixed groups of cells or the fixed groups of group of cells?*

Question 2.2. *What are the best descriptions for the “Cancer’s Recognition” in terms of these messy and dense SuperHyperModels where embedded notions are illustrated?*

It’s motivation to find notions to use in this dense model is titled “SuperHyperGraphs”. Thus it motivates us to define different types of “ SuperHyperStable-Cut” and “Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut” on “SuperHyperGraph” and “Extreme SuperHyperGraph”. Then the research has taken more motivations to define SuperHyperClasses and to find some connections amid this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions. It motivates us to get some instances and examples to make clarifications about the framework of this research. The general results and some results about some connections are some avenues to make key point of this research, “Cancer’s Recognition”, more understandable and more clear.

The framework of this research is as follows. In the beginning, I introduce basic definitions to clarify about preliminaries. In the subsection “Preliminaries”, initial definitions about SuperHyperGraphs and Extreme SuperHyperGraph are deeply-introduced and in-depth-discussed. The elementary concepts are clarified and illustrated completely and sometimes review literature are applied to make sense about what’s going to figure out about the upcoming sections. The main definitions and their clarifications alongside some results about new notions, SuperHyperStable-Cut and Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut, are figured out in sections “ SuperHyperStable-Cut”

and “Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut”. In the sense of tackling on getting results and in Stable-Cut to make sense about continuing the research, the ideas of SuperHyperUniform and Extreme SuperHyperUniform are introduced and as their consequences, corresponded SuperHyperClasses are figured out to debut what’s done in this section, titled “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses”. As going back to origin of the notions, there are some smart steps toward the common notions to extend the new notions in new frameworks, SuperHyperGraph and Extreme SuperHyperGraph, in the sections “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses”. The starter research about the general SuperHyperRelations and as concluding and closing section of theoretical research are contained in the section “General Results”. Some general SuperHyperRelations are fundamental and they are well-known as fundamental SuperHyperNotions as elicited and discussed in the sections, “General Results”, “SuperHyperStable-Cut”, “Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut”, “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses”. There are curious questions about what’s done about the SuperHyperNotions to make sense about excellency of this research and going to figure out the word “best” as the description and adjective for this research as presented in section, “ SuperHyperStable-Cut”. The keyword of this research debut in the section “Applications in Cancer’s Recognition” with two cases and subsections “Case 1: The Initial Steps Toward SuperHyperBipartite as SuperHyperModel” and “Case 2: The Increasing Steps Toward SuperHyperMultipartite as SuperHyperModel”. In the section, “Open Problems”, there are some scrutiny and discernment on what’s done and what’s happened in this research in the terms of “questions” and “problems” to make sense to figure out this research in featured style. The advantages and the limitations of this research alongside about what’s done in this research to make sense and to get sense about what’s figured out are included in the section, “Conclusion and Closing Remarks”.

3 Extreme Preliminaries Of This Scientific Research On the Redeemed Ways

In this section, the basic material in this scientific research, is referred to [Single Valued Neutrosophic Set](**Ref. [120]**,Definition 2.2,p.2), [Neutrosophic Set](**Ref. [120]**,Definition 2.1,p.1), [Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [120]**,Definition 2.5,p.2), [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [120]**,Definition 2.7,p.3), [t-norm](**Ref. [120]**, Definition 2.7, p.3), and [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](**Ref. [120]**,Definition 2.7,p.3), [Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths] (**Ref. [120]**,Definition 5.3,p.7), and [Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)] (**Ref. [120]**,Definition 5.4,p.7). Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are addressed to **Ref. [120]**.

In this subsection, the basic material which is used in this scientific research, is presented. Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are elicited.

Definition 3.1 (Neutrosophic Set). (**Ref. [120]**,Definition 2.1,p.1).

Let X be a Stable-Cut of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x ; then the **Neutrosophic set** A (NS A) is an object having the form

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$$

where the functions $T, I, F : X \rightarrow]-0, 1^+[$ define respectively the a **truth-membership function**, an **indeterminacy-membership function**, and a

falsity-membership function of the element $x \in X$ to the set A with the condition

$$-0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3^+.$$

The functions $T_A(x)$, $I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ are real standard or nonstandard subsets of $]^{-}0, 1^{+}[$.

Definition 3.2 (Single Valued Neutrosophic Set). (**Ref.** [120], Definition 2.2, p.2).

Let X be a Stable-Cut of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x . A **single valued Neutrosophic set** A (SVNS A) is characterized by truth-membership function $T_A(x)$, an indeterminacy-membership function $I_A(x)$, and a falsity-membership function $F_A(x)$. For each point x in X , $T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \in [0, 1]$. A SVNS A can be written as

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}.$$

Definition 3.3. The **degree of truth-membership**, **indeterminacy-membership** and **falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$T_A(X) = \min[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = \min[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$\text{and } F_A(X) = \min[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.4. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{ x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0 \}.$$

Definition 3.5 (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (**Ref.** [120], Definition 2.5, p.2).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'})) : T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (ix) and the following conditions hold:

$$T'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$I'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$\text{and } F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}}$$

where $i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$.

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_V(E_{i'}), T''_V(E_{i'})$, and $T'''_V(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the ii' th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Definition 3.6 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [120], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;
- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**;
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**;
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**;
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**;
- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**.

If we choose different types of binary operations, then we could get hugely diverse types of general forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG).

Definition 3.7 (t-norm). (Ref. [120], Definition 2.7, p.3).

A binary operation $\otimes : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a **t-norm** if it satisfies the following for $x, y, z, w \in [0, 1]$:

- (i) $1 \otimes x = x$;
- (ii) $x \otimes y = y \otimes x$;
- (iii) $x \otimes (y \otimes z) = (x \otimes y) \otimes z$;
- (iv) If $w \leq x$ and $y \leq z$ then $w \otimes y \leq x \otimes z$.

Definition 3.8. The **degree of truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership and falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$ (with respect to t-norm T_{norm}):

$$T_A(X) = T_{norm}[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = T_{norm}[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

and $F_A(X) = T_{norm}[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}$.

Definition 3.9. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0\}.$$

Definition 3.10. (General Forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'})) : T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$).

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_V(E_{i'})$, $I'_V(E_{i'})$, and $F'_V(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the ii' th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Definition 3.11 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [120], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;
- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**;
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**;
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**;
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**;

(vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**.

This SuperHyperModel is too messy and too dense. Thus there's a need to have some restrictions and conditions on SuperHyperGraph. The special case of this SuperHyperGraph makes the patterns and regularities.

Definition 3.12. A graph is **SuperHyperUniform** if it's SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same.

To get more visions on SuperHyperUniform, the some SuperHyperClasses are introduced. It makes to have SuperHyperUniform more understandable.

Definition 3.13. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as follows.

- (i). It's **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions;
- (ii). it's **SuperHyperCycle** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges;
- (iii). it's **SuperHyperStar** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges;
- (iv). it's **SuperHyperBipartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common;
- (v). it's **SuperHyperMultiPartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common;
- (vi). it's **SuperHyperWheel** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex.

Definition 3.14. Let a pair $S = (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S . Then a sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s$$

is called a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s if either of following conditions hold:

- (i) $V_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (ii) there's a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ such that $v_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (iii) there's a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ such that $V'_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (iv) there's a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (v) there's a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (vi) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (vii) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;

- (viii) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 464
- (ix) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that 465
 $V'_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$. 466

Definition 3.15. (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths). 467

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

could be characterized as follow-up items. 468

- (i) If for all $V_i, E_{j'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, $|E_{j'}| = 2$, then NSHP is called **path**; 469
- (ii) if for all $E_{j'}$, $|E_{j'}| = 2$, and there's V_i , $|V_i| \geq 1$, then NSHP is called **SuperPath**; 470
- (iii) if for all $V_i, E_{j'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, $|E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **HyperPath**; 471
- (iv) if there are $V_i, E_{j'}$, $|V_i| \geq 1$, $|E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** . 472
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Definition 3.16 (Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths). 474

(Ref. [120], Definition 5.3, p.7). 475

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

have 476

- (i) **Neutrosophic t-strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, m, n)_{i=1}^s$; 477
- (ii) **Neutrosophic i-strength** $(m, \min\{I(V_i)\}, n)_{i=1}^s$; 478
- (iii) **Neutrosophic f-strength** $(m, n, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$; 479
- (iv) **Neutrosophic strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$. 480

Definition 3.17 (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)). (Ref. [120], Definition 5.4, p.7). 481
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Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called 483
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- (ix) **Neutrosophic t-connective** if $T(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic t-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 485
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- (x) **Neutrosophic i-connective** if $I(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic i-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 488
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- (xi) **Neutrosophic f-connective** if $F(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic f-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 491
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- (xii) **Neutrosophic connective** if $(T(E), I(E), F(E)) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$.

Definition 3.18. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut criteria** holds

E' is Stable;

- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut criteria** holds

E' is Stable;

and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;

- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut criteria** holds

V' is Stable;

- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut criteria** holds

V' is Stable;

and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;

- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut.

Definition 3.19. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable-Cut).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut;

- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum

- Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut; 531-534
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 535-544
- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient; 545-555
- (v) an **Extreme V-SuperHyperStable-Cut** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut; 556-563
- (vi) a **Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperStable-Cut** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut; 564-571
- (vii) an **Extreme V-SuperHyperStable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the 572-580

Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

- (viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperStable-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperStable-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperStable-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality consecutive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

Definition 3.20. ((Extreme/Neutrosophic) δ -SuperHyperStable-Cut).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Then

- (i) an δ -**SuperHyperStable-Cut** is a Neutrosophic kind of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut such that either of the following expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$:

$$\begin{aligned} |S \cap N(s)| &> |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta; \\ |S \cap N(s)| &< |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta. \end{aligned}$$

The Expression (3.1), holds if S is an δ -**SuperHyperOffensive**. And the Expression (3.1), holds if S is an δ -**SuperHyperDefensive**;

- (ii) a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperStable-Cut** is a Neutrosophic kind of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut such that either of the following Neutrosophic expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$:

$$\begin{aligned} |S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} &> |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta; \\ |S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} &< |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta. \end{aligned}$$

The Expression (3.1), holds if S is a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperOffensive**. And the Expression (3.1), holds if S is a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperDefensive**.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, there's a need to "redefine" the notion of "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.21. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. It's redefined **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** if the Table (1) holds.

It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic more understandable.

Definition 3.22. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. There are some **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses** if the Table (2) holds. Thus Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, SuperHyperStable-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are

Table 1. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.23)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Table 2. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, Mentioned in the Definition (3.22)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar, Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite, and Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel if the Table (2) holds.

It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut. Since there's more ways to get type-results to make a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut more Neutrosophically understandable.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut, there's a need to "redefine" the Neutrosophic notion of "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.23. Assume a SuperHyperStable-Cut. It's redefined a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable-Cut** if the Table (3) holds.

4 Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 4.1. (Extreme event).

Table 3. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.23)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Any Extreme k -subset of A of V is called **Extreme k -event** and if $k = 2$, then Extreme subset of A of V is called **Extreme event**. The following expression is called **Extreme probability** of A .

$$E(A) = \sum_{a \in A} E(a). \quad (4.1)$$

Definition 4.2. (Extreme Independent).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. s Extreme k -events A_i , $i \in I$ is called **Extreme s-independent criteria** if the following expression is called **Extreme s-independent criteria**

$$E(\cap_{i \in I} A_i) = \prod_{i \in I} P(A_i).$$

And if $s = 2$, then Extreme k -events of A and B is called **Extreme independent**. The following expression is called **Extreme independent criteria**

$$E(A \cap B) = P(A)P(B). \quad (4.2)$$

Definition 4.3. (Extreme Variable).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Any k -function Stable-Cut like E is called **Extreme k -Variable**. If $k = 2$, then any 2-function Stable-Cut like E is called **Extreme Variable**.

The notion of independent on Extreme Variable is likewise.

Definition 4.4. (Extreme Expectation).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. A Extreme k -Variable E has a number is called **Extreme Expectation** if the following expression is called **Extreme Expectation criteria**

$$Ex(E) = \sum_{\alpha \in V} E(\alpha)P(\alpha).$$

Definition 4.5. (Extreme Crossing).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. A Extreme number is called **Extreme Crossing** if the following expression is called **Extreme Crossing criteria**

$$Cr(S) = \min\{\text{Number of Crossing in a Plane Embedding of } S\}.$$

Lemma 4.6. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Let m and n propose special Stable-Cut. Then with $m \geq 4n$,

Proof. Consider a planar embedding G of G with $cr(G)$ crossings. Let S be a Extreme random k -subset of V obtained by choosing each SuperHyperVertex of G Extreme independently with probability Stable-Cut $p := 4n/m$, and set $H := G[S]$ and $H := G[S]$.

Define random variables X, Y, Z on V as follows: X is the Extreme number of SuperHyperVertices, Y the Extreme number of SuperHyperEdges, and Z the Extreme

number of crossings of H . The trivial bound noted above, when applied to H , yields the inequality $Z \geq cr(H) \geq Y - 3X$. By linearity of Extreme Expectation,

$$E(Z) \geq E(Y) - 3E(X).$$

Now $E(X) = pn$, $E(Y) = p^2m$ (each SuperHyperEdge having some SuperHyperEnds) and $E(Z) = p^4cr(G)$ (each crossing being defined by some SuperHyperVertices). Hence

$$p^4cr(G) \geq p^2m - 3pn.$$

Dividing both sides by p^4 , we have:

$$cr(G) \geq \frac{pm - 3n}{p^3} = \frac{n}{(4n/m)^3} = \frac{1}{64}m^3n^2.$$

□ 673

Theorem 4.7. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Let P be a SuperHyperSet of n points in the plane, and let l be the Extreme number of SuperHyperLines in the plane passing through at least $k + 1$ of these points, where $1 \leq k \leq 2\sqrt{2n}$. Then $l < 32n^2/k^3$.

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Proof. Form a Extreme SuperHyperGraph G with SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet P whose SuperHyperEdge are the segments between consecutive points on the SuperHyperLines which pass through at least $k + 1$ points of P . This Extreme SuperHyperGraph has at least kl SuperHyperEdges and Extreme crossing at most l choose two. Thus either $kl < 4n$, in which case $l < 4n/k \leq 32n^2/k^3$, or $l^2/2 > 1$ choose $2 \geq cr(G) \geq (kl)^3/64n^2$ by the Extreme Crossing Lemma, and again $l < 32n^2/k^3$.

□ 684

Theorem 4.8. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Let P be a SuperHyperSet of n points in the plane, and let k be the number of pairs of points of P at unit SuperHyperDistance. Then $k < 5n^{4/3}$.

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Proof. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Draw a SuperHyperUnit SuperHyperCircle around each SuperHyperPoint of P . Let n_i be the Extreme number of these SuperHyperCircles passing through exactly i points of P . Then $\sum i = 0^{n-1}n_i = n$ and $k = \frac{1}{2} \sum i = 0^{n-1}in_i$. Now form a Extreme SuperHyperGraph H with SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet P whose SuperHyperEdges are the SuperHyperArcs between consecutive SuperHyperPoints on the SuperHyperCircles that pass through at least three SuperHyperPoints of P . Then

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$$e(H) = \sum_{i=3}^{n-1} in_i = 2k - n_1 - 2n_2 \geq 2k - 2n.$$

Some SuperHyperPairs of SuperHyperVertices of H might be joined by some parallel SuperHyperEdges. Delete from H one of each SuperHyperPair of parallel SuperHyperEdges, so as to obtain a simple Extreme SuperHyperGraph G with $e(G) \geq k - n$. Now $cr(G) \leq n(n - 1)$ because G is formed from at most n SuperHyperCircles, and any two SuperHyperCircles cross at most twice. Thus either $e(G) < 4n$, in which case $k < 5n < 5n^{4/3}$, or $n^2 > n(n - 1) \geq cr(G) \geq (k - n)^3/64n^2$ by the Extreme Crossing Lemma, and $k < 4n^{4/3} + n < 5n^{4/3}$.

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Proposition 4.9. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Let X be a nonnegative Extreme Variable and t a positive real number. Then

$$P(X \geq t) \leq \frac{E(X)}{t}.$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} E(X) &= \sum \{X(a)P(a) : a \in V\} \geq \sum \{X(a)P(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} \\ &= \sum \{tP(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} = t \sum \{P(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} \\ &= tP(X \geq t). \end{aligned}$$

Dividing the first and last members by t yields the asserted inequality. $\square$

Corollary 4.10. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Let X_n be a nonnegative integer-valued variable in a probability Stable-Cut (V_n, E_n) , $n \geq 1$. If $E(X_n) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, then $P(X_n = 0) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Proof.

Theorem 4.11. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. A special SuperHyperGraph in $G_{n,p}$ almost surely has stability number at most $\lceil 2p^{-1} \log n \rceil$.

Proof. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. A special SuperHyperGraph in $G_{n,p}$ is up. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ and let S be a given SuperHyperSet of $k+1$ SuperHyperVertices of G , where $k \in \mathbb{N}$. The probability that S is a stable SuperHyperSet of G is $(1-p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}$, this being the probability that none of the $\binom{k+1}{2}$ pairs of SuperHyperVertices of S is a SuperHyperEdge of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph G .

Let A_S denote the event that S is a stable SuperHyperSet of G , and let X_S denote the indicator Extreme Variable for this Extreme Event. By equation, we have

$$E(X_S) = P(X_S = 1) = P(A_S) = (1-p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}.$$

Let X be the number of stable SuperHyperSets of cardinality $k+1$ in G . Then

$$X = \sum \{X_S : S \subseteq V, |S| = k+1\}$$

and so, by those,

$$E(X) = \sum \{E(X_S) : S \subseteq V, |S| = k+1\} = \binom{n}{k+1} (1-p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}.$$

We bound the right-hand side by invoking two elementary inequalities:

$$\binom{n}{k+1} \leq \frac{n^{k+1}}{(k+1)!} \text{ and } 1-p \leq e^{-p}.$$

This yields the following upper bound on $E(X)$.

$$E(X) \leq \frac{n^{k+1} e^{-p \binom{k+1}{2}}}{(k+1)!} = \frac{n e^{-pk/2}}{(k+1)!}$$

Suppose now that $k = \lceil 2p^{-1} \log n \rceil$. Then $k \geq 2p^{-1} \log n$, so $n e^{-pk/2} \leq 1$. Because k grows at least as fast as the logarithm of n , implies that $E(X) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Because X is integer-valued and nonnegative, we deduce from Corollary that $P(X = 0) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Consequently, a Extreme SuperHyperGraph in $\mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely has stability number at most k . $\square$

Definition 4.12. (Extreme Variance). 733

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. A Extreme k-Variable E has a number is called **Extreme Variance** if the following expression is called **Extreme Variance criteria** 734
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$$Vx(E) = Ex((X - Ex(X))^2).$$

Theorem 4.13. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Let X be a Extreme Variable and let t be a positive real number. Then 737
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$$E(|X - Ex(X)| \geq t) \leq \frac{V(X)}{t^2}.$$

Proof. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Let X be a Extreme Variable and let t be a positive real number. Then 740
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$$E(|X - Ex(X)| \geq t) = E((X - Ex(X))^2 \geq t^2) \leq \frac{Ex((X - Ex(X))^2)}{t^2} = \frac{V(X)}{t^2}.$$

□ 743

Corollary 4.14. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Let X_n be a Extreme Variable in a probability Stable-Cut $(V_n, E_n), n \geq 1$. If $Ex(X_n) \neq 0$ and $V(X_n) \ll E^2(X_n)$, then 744
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$$E(X_n = 0) \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

Proof. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Set $X := X_n$ and $t := |Ex(X_n)|$ in Chebyshev's Inequality, and observe that $E(X_n = 0) \leq E(|X_n - Ex(X_n)| \geq |Ex(X_n)|)$ because $|X_n - Ex(X_n)| = |Ex(X_n)|$ when $X_n = 0$. 747
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Theorem 4.15. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,1/2}$. For $0 \leq k \leq n$, set $f(k) := (n \text{ choose } k)2^{-(k \text{ choose } 2)}$ and let k^* be the least value of k for which $f(k)$ is less than one. Then almost surely $\alpha(G)$ takes one of the three values $k^* - 2, k^* - 1, k^*$. 751
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Proof. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. As in the proof of related Theorem, the result is straightforward. 755
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Corollary 4.16. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,1/2}$ and let f and k^* be as defined in previous Theorem. Then either: 758
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(i). $f(k^*) \ll 1$, in which case almost surely $\alpha(G)$ is equal to either $k^* - 2$ or $k^* - 1$,
or 761
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(ii). $f(k^* - 1) \gg 1$, in which case almost surely $\alpha(G)$ is equal to either $k^* - 1$ or k^* . 763

Proof. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. The latter is straightforward. 764
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Definition 4.17. (Extreme Threshold). 766

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Let P be a monotone property of SuperHyperGraphs (one which is preserved when SuperHyperEdges are added). Then a **Extreme Threshold** for P is a function $f(n)$ such that: 767
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(i). if $p \ll f(n)$, then $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely does not have P ,

(ii). if $p \gg f(n)$, then $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely has P .

Definition 4.18. (Extreme Balanced).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Let F be a fixed Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then there is a threshold function for the property of containing a copy of F as a Extreme SubSuperHyperGraph is called **Extreme Balanced**.

Theorem 4.19. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. Let F be a nonempty balanced Extreme SubSuperHyperGraph with k SuperHyperVertices and l SuperHyperEdges. Then $n^{-k/l}$ is a threshold function for the property of containing F as a Extreme SubSuperHyperGraph.

Proof. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Stable-Cut. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 4.20. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items.

- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut.

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^4. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^4. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut}} \\ &= \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1,2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut.

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^4. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^4. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut}} \\ &= \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1,2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Figure 1. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 2. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 3. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^4. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^4. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut}} &= \{V_i\}_{i \neq 1,2}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} &= \{E_i\}_{i \neq 1,5}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^3. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut}} &= \{V_i\}_{i=1,4}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 12z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely

Figure 4. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} &= \{\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut}} &= \{V_1, V_6, V_{15}, V_9\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3 \times 4 \times 3z^4.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} &= \{E_{2i+1_{i=0^4}}, E_{2j+23_{i=0^4}}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2 \times 2z^{10}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0^4}}, V_{2j+11_{i=0^4}}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2 \times 2z^{10}.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely

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Figure 5. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 6. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 7. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} &= \\
 &\{E_{2i+1}_{i=0^4}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^5. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut}} &= \\
 &\{V_{2i+1}_{i=0^4}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^5.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} &= \\
 &\{E_1, E_2, E_3\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut}} &= \\
 &\{V_3, V_6, V_8\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely

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Figure 8. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} &= \{E_{2i+1_{i=0^4}}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^5. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0^4}}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^5.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} &= \{E_1, E_2, E_3\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut}} &= \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

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Figure 9. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 10. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 11. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} &= \\
 &= \{E_6, E_7, E_8\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 &= z^3. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut}} &= \\
 &= \{V_1, V_6\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 &= 3 \times 3z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} &= \\
 &= \{E_i\}_{i=2,3,4,5,6}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 &= z^5. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut}} &= \\
 &= \{V_i\}_{i=4,5,6,9,10}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 &= 2z^5.
 \end{aligned}$$

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Figure 12. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 845
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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} &= \\
 &\{E_6, E_7, E_8\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 &= z^3. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut}} &= \\
 &\{V_1, V_6\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 &= 3 \times 3z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 848
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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} &= \\
 &= \{E_1\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 &= 2z. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut}} &= \{V_2, V_3\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely 852
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Figure 13. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 14. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 15. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

straightforward.

855

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{E_{2i+1}_{i=0,2}\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 2z^3. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{V_{2i+2}_{i=0,1}, V_5\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 2z^3.
 \end{aligned}$$

856

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{E_{2i+1}_{i=0,2}\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 2z^3. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{V_1, V_3, V_{10}, V_{22}\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 3 \times 4 \times 5z^4.
 \end{aligned}$$

860

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely

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Figure 16. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

straightforward.

863

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{E_{2i+1, i=0,2}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 2z^3. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_{10}, V_{22}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 7 \times 4 \times 4 \times 5z^4.
 \end{aligned}$$

864

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{E_{2i+1, i=0,2}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 2z^3. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_{10}, V_{22}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 7 \times 4 \times 4 \times 5z^4.
 \end{aligned}$$

868

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely

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Figure 17. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 18. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 19. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

straightforward.

871

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{E_{2i+1, i=0^5}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 2z^6. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{V_{E_{2i+1, i=0^5}}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 2z^6.
 \end{aligned}$$

872

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\text{INTERNAL SuperHyperVERTICES}\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= az^{10}.
 \end{aligned}$$

876

Figure 21. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 22. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Proposition 4.21. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices belong to any Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Cut if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Extreme SuperHyperVertex, some interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices are mutually Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors with no Extreme exception at all minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them.

Proposition 4.22. Assume a connected non-obvious Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only the maximum possibilities of the distinct interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices inside of any given Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Cut minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them. In other words, there's only an unique Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only two distinct Extreme SuperHyperVertices in an Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Cut, minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them.

Proposition 4.23. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. If a Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Extreme SuperHyperVertices, then the Extreme cardinality of the Extreme R-Stable-Cut is at least

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

It's straightforward that the Extreme cardinality of the Extreme R-Stable-Cut is at least the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges with the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges. In other words, the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges contains the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices are renamed to Extreme Stable-Cut in some cases but the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdge with the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices, has the Extreme SuperHyperVertices are contained in a Extreme R-Stable-Cut.

Proposition 4.24. Assume a simple Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then the Extreme number of type-result-R-Stable-Cut has, the least Extreme cardinality, the lower sharp Extreme bound for Extreme cardinality, is the Extreme cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_{E'}, c_{E''}, c_{E'''}\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

If there's a Extreme type-result-R-Stable-Cut with the least Extreme cardinality, the lower sharp Extreme bound for cardinality. 907
908

Proposition 4.25. Assume a connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then in the worst case, literally, 909
910

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Cut} = \{V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, E_3, V_4, E_4, V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = z^4.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Cut} = \{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4, V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = z^5.$$

Is a Extreme type-result-Stable-Cut. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of a Extreme type-result-Stable-Cut is the cardinality of 911
912

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Cut} = \{V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, E_3, V_4, E_4, V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = z^4.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Cut} = \{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4, V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = z^5.$$

Proof. Assume a connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The SuperHyperSet of the SuperHyperVertices $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ isn't a quasi-R-Stable-Cut since neither amount of Extreme SuperHyperEdges nor amount of SuperHyperVertices where amount refers to the Extreme number of SuperHyperVertices(-/SuperHyperEdges) more than one to form any kind of SuperHyperEdges or any number of SuperHyperEdges. Let us consider the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E,E'=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

This Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices has the eligibilities to propose property such that there's no Extreme SuperHyperVertex of a Extreme SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Extreme SuperHyperEdge for all Extreme SuperHyperVertices but the maximum Extreme cardinality indicates that these Extreme type-SuperHyperSets couldn't give us the Extreme lower bound in the term of Extreme sharpness. In other words, the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E,E'=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices implies at least on-quasi-triangle style is up but sometimes the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E,E'=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices is free-quasi-triangle and it doesn't make a contradiction to the supposition on the connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Thus the minimum case never happens in the generality of the connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraphs. Thus if we assume in the worst case, literally,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is a quasi-R-Stable-Cut. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of a quasi-R-Stable-Cut is the cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

Then we've lost some connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperClasses of the connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraphs titled free-triangle, on-triangle, and their quasi-types but the SuperHyperStable is only up in this quasi-R-Stable-Cut. It's the contradiction to that fact on the generality. There are some counterexamples to deny this statement. One of them comes from the setting of the graph titled path and cycle as the counterexamples-classes or reversely direction star as the examples-classes, are well-known classes in that setting and they could be considered as the examples-classes and counterexamples-classes for the tight bound of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

Let $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ in mind. There's no necessity on the SuperHyperEdge since we need at least two SuperHyperVertices to form a SuperHyperEdge. It doesn't withdraw the principles of the main definition since there's no condition to be satisfied but the condition is on the existence of the SuperHyperEdge instead of acting on the SuperHyperVertices. In other words, if there's a SuperHyperEdge, then the Extreme SuperHyperSet has the necessary condition for the intended definition to be applied. Thus the $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ is withdrawn not by the conditions of the main definition but by the necessity of the pre-condition on the usage of the main definition.

The Extreme structure of the Extreme R-Stable-Cut decorates the Extreme SuperHyperVertices don't have received any Extreme connections so as this Extreme style implies different versions of Extreme SuperHyperEdges with the maximum Extreme cardinality in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperVertices are spotlight. The lower Extreme bound is to have the maximum Extreme groups of Extreme SuperHyperVertices have perfect Extreme connections inside each of SuperHyperEdges and the outside of this Extreme SuperHyperSet doesn't matter but regarding the connectedness of the used Extreme SuperHyperGraph arising from its Extreme properties taken from the fact that it's simple. If there's no more than one Extreme SuperHyperVertex in the targeted Extreme SuperHyperSet, then there's no Extreme connection. Furthermore, the Extreme existence of one Extreme SuperHyperVertex has no Extreme effect to talk about the Extreme R-Stable-Cut. Since at least two Extreme SuperHyperVertices involve to make a title in the Extreme background of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph. The Extreme SuperHyperGraph is obvious if it has no Extreme SuperHyperEdge but at least two Extreme SuperHyperVertices make the Extreme version of Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the Extreme setting of non-obvious Extreme SuperHyperGraph, there are at least one Extreme SuperHyperEdge. It's necessary to mention that the word "Simple" is used as Extreme adjective for the initial Extreme SuperHyperGraph, induces there's no Extreme appearance of the loop Extreme version of the Extreme SuperHyperEdge and this Extreme SuperHyperGraph is said to be loopless. The Extreme adjective "loop" on the basic Extreme framework engages one Extreme SuperHyperVertex but it never happens in this Extreme setting. With these Extreme bases, on a Extreme SuperHyperGraph, there's at least one Extreme SuperHyperEdge thus there's at least a Extreme R-Stable-Cut has the Extreme cardinality of a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus, a Extreme R-Stable-Cut has the Extreme cardinality at least a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperSet $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$. This Extreme SuperHyperSet isn't a Extreme R-Stable-Cut since either the Extreme SuperHyperGraph is an obvious Extreme SuperHyperModel thus it never happens since there's no Extreme usage of this Extreme framework and even more there's no Extreme connection inside or the Extreme SuperHyperGraph isn't

obvious and as its consequences, there's a Extreme contradiction with the term "Extreme R-Stable-Cut" since the maximum Extreme cardinality never happens for this Extreme style of the Extreme SuperHyperSet and beyond that there's no Extreme connection inside as mentioned in first Extreme case in the forms of drawback for this selected Extreme SuperHyperSet. Let

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E'} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\}$$

Comes up. This Extreme case implies having the Extreme style of on-quasi-triangle Extreme style on the every Extreme elements of this Extreme SuperHyperSet. Precisely, the Extreme R-Stable-Cut is the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that some Extreme amount of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices are on-quasi-triangle Extreme style. The Extreme cardinality of the v SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E'} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\}$$

Is the maximum in comparison to the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\} \cdot$$

But the lower Extreme bound is up. Thus the minimum Extreme cardinality of the maximum Extreme cardinality ends up the Extreme discussion. The first Extreme term refers to the Extreme setting of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph but this key point is enough since there's a Extreme SuperHyperClass of a Extreme SuperHyperGraph has no on-quasi-triangle Extreme style amid some amount of its Extreme SuperHyperVertices. This Extreme setting of the Extreme SuperHyperModel proposes a Extreme SuperHyperSet has only some amount Extreme SuperHyperVertices from one Extreme SuperHyperEdge such that there's no Extreme amount of Extreme SuperHyperEdges more than one involving these some amount of these Extreme SuperHyperVertices. The Extreme cardinality of this Extreme SuperHyperSet is the maximum and the Extreme case is occurred in the minimum Extreme situation. To sum them up, the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\} \cdot$$

Has the maximum Extreme cardinality such that

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\} \cdot$$

Contains some Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's distinct-covers-order-amount Extreme SuperHyperEdges for amount of Extreme SuperHyperVertices taken from the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\} \cdot$$

It means that the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\} \cdot$$

Is a Extreme R-Stable-Cut for the Extreme SuperHyperGraph as used Extreme background in the Extreme terms of worst Extreme case and the common theme of the lower Extreme bound occurred in the specific Extreme SuperHyperClasses of the Extreme SuperHyperGraphs which are Extreme free-quasi-triangle.

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Assume a Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Extreme number of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices. Then every Extreme SuperHyperVertex has at least one Extreme SuperHyperEdge with others in common. Thus those Extreme SuperHyperVertices have the eligibles to be contained in a Extreme R-Stable-Cut. Those Extreme SuperHyperVertices are potentially included in a Extreme style-R-Stable-Cut. Formally, consider

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

Are the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. Thus

$$Z_i \sim Z_j, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z.$$

where the $\sim$ isn't an equivalence relation but only the symmetric relation on the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph. The formal definition is as follows.

$$Z_i \sim Z_j, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z$$

if and only if Z_i and Z_j are the Extreme SuperHyperVertices and there's only and only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ between the Extreme SuperHyperVertices Z_i and Z_j . The other definition for the Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ in the terms of Extreme R-Stable-Cut is

$$\{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}.$$

This definition coincides with the definition of the Extreme R-Stable-Cut but with slightly differences in the maximum Extreme cardinality amid those Extreme type-SuperHyperSets of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$\max_z |\{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid Z_i \sim Z_j, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z\}|_{\text{Extreme cardinality}},$$

and

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

is formalized with mathematical literatures on the Extreme R-Stable-Cut. Let $Z_i \overset{E}{\sim} Z_j$, be defined as Z_i and Z_j are the Extreme SuperHyperVertices belong to the Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. Thus,

$$E = \{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid Z_i \overset{E}{\sim} Z_j, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z\}.$$

Or

$$\{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

But with the slightly differences,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Extreme R-Stable-Cut} = \\ \{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid \forall i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z, \exists E_x, Z_i \overset{E_x}{\sim} Z_j\}. \end{aligned}$$

Extreme R-Stable-Cut =

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

Thus $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ is a Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Cut where $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ is fixed that means $E_x = E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. for all Extreme intended SuperHyperVertices

but in a Extreme Stable-Cut, $E_x = E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ could be different and it's not unique. To sum them up, in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. If a Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Extreme SuperHyperVertices, then the Extreme cardinality of the Extreme R-Stable-Cut is at least

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

It's straightforward that the Extreme cardinality of the Extreme R-Stable-Cut is at least the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges with the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges. In other words, the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges contains the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices are renamed to Extreme Stable-Cut in some cases but the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdge with the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices, has the Extreme SuperHyperVertices are contained in a Extreme R-Stable-Cut.

The obvious SuperHyperGraph has no Extreme SuperHyperEdges. But the non-obvious Extreme SuperHyperModel is up. The quasi-SuperHyperModel addresses some issues about the Extreme optimal SuperHyperObject. It specially delivers some remarks on the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's distinct amount of Extreme SuperHyperEdges for distinct amount of Extreme SuperHyperVertices up to all taken from that Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices but this Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices is either has the maximum Extreme SuperHyperCardinality or it doesn't have maximum Extreme SuperHyperCardinality. In a non-obvious SuperHyperModel, there's at least one Extreme SuperHyperEdge containing at least all Extreme SuperHyperVertices. Thus it forms a Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Cut where the Extreme completion of the Extreme incidence is up in that. Thus it's, literarily, a Extreme embedded R-Stable-Cut. The SuperHyperNotions of embedded SuperHyperSet and quasi-SuperHyperSet coincide. In the original setting, these types of SuperHyperSets only don't satisfy on the maximum SuperHyperCardinality. Thus the embedded setting is elected such that those SuperHyperSets have the maximum Extreme SuperHyperCardinality and they're Extreme SuperHyperOptimal. The less than two distinct types of Extreme SuperHyperVertices are included in the minimum Extreme style of the embedded Extreme R-Stable-Cut. The interior types of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices are deciders. Since the Extreme number of SuperHyperNeighbors are only affected by the interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices. The common connections, more precise and more formal, the perfect unique connections inside the Extreme SuperHyperSet for any distinct types of Extreme SuperHyperVertices pose the Extreme R-Stable-Cut. Thus Extreme exterior SuperHyperVertices could be used only in one Extreme SuperHyperEdge and in Extreme SuperHyperRelation with the interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices in that Extreme SuperHyperEdge. In the embedded Extreme Stable-Cut, there's the usage of exterior Extreme SuperHyperVertices since they've more connections inside more than outside. Thus the title "exterior" is more relevant than the title "interior". One Extreme SuperHyperVertex has no connection, inside. Thus, the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices with one SuperHyperElement has been ignored in the exploring to lead on the optimal case implying the Extreme R-Stable-Cut. The Extreme R-Stable-Cut with the exclusion of the exclusion of all Extreme SuperHyperVertices in one Extreme SuperHyperEdge and with other terms, the Extreme R-Stable-Cut with the inclusion of all Extreme SuperHyperVertices in one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, is a Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Cut. To sum them up, in a connected non-obvious Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only the maximum possibilities of the distinct interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices inside of any given Extreme

quasi-R-Stable-Cut minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them. In other words, there's only an unique Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only two distinct Extreme SuperHyperVertices in an Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Cut, minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them.

The main definition of the Extreme R-Stable-Cut has two titles. a Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Cut and its corresponded quasi-maximum Extreme R-SuperHyperCardinality are two titles in the terms of quasi-R-styles. For any Extreme number, there's a Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Cut with that quasi-maximum Extreme SuperHyperCardinality in the terms of the embedded Extreme SuperHyperGraph. If there's an embedded Extreme SuperHyperGraph, then the Extreme quasi-SuperHyperNotions lead us to take the collection of all the Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Cuts for all Extreme numbers less than its Extreme corresponded maximum number. The essence of the Extreme Stable-Cut ends up but this essence starts up in the terms of the Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Cut, again and more in the operations of collecting all the Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Cuts acted on the all possible used formations of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph to achieve one Extreme number. This Extreme number is

considered as the equivalence class for all corresponded quasi-R-Stable-Cuts. Let $z_{\text{Extreme Number}}$, $S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}$ and $G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}}$ be a Extreme number, a Extreme SuperHyperSet and a Extreme Stable-Cut. Then

$$\begin{aligned} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} &= \{S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ &S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}}, \\ &|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Extreme Number}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

As its consequences, the formal definition of the Extreme Stable-Cut is re-formalized and redefined as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} &= \\ \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ &S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}}, \\ &|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Extreme Number}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

To get more precise perceptions, the follow-up expressions propose another formal technical definition for the Extreme Stable-Cut.

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} &= \\ \{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} &= \\ \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ &S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}}, \\ &|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \mid \\ &|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

In more concise and more convenient ways, the modified definition for the Extreme

Stable-Cut poses the upcoming expressions. 1000

$$\begin{aligned}
 G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} &= \\
 \{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
 |S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
 &= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

To translate the statement to this mathematical literature, the formulae will be revised. 1001

$$\begin{aligned}
 G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} &= \\
 \{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
 |S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
 &= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \\
 &= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

And then, 1002

$$\begin{aligned}
 G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} &= \\
 \{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
 |S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
 &= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

To get more visions in the closer look-up, there's an overall overlook. 1003

$$\begin{aligned}
 G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} &= \\
 \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\
 S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} &= G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}}, \\
 |S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
 &= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} &= \\
 \{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} &= \\
 \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\
 S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} &= G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}}, \\
 |S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
 &= z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \mid \\
 |S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
 &= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} &= \\
 \{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
 |S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
 &= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \\
 &= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} &= \\
&\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
&|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

Now, the extension of these types of approaches is up. Since the new term, “Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood”, could be redefined as the collection of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that any amount of its Extreme SuperHyperVertices are incident to a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. It’s, literarily, another name for “Extreme Quasi-Stable-Cut” but, precisely, it’s the generalization of “Extreme Quasi-Stable-Cut” since “Extreme Quasi-Stable-Cut” happens “Extreme Stable-Cut” in a Extreme SuperHyperGraph as initial framework and background but “Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood” may not happens “Extreme Stable-Cut” in a Extreme SuperHyperGraph as initial framework and preliminarily background since there are some ambiguities about the Extreme SuperHyperCardinality arise from it. To get orderly keywords, the terms, “Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood”, “Extreme Quasi-Stable-Cut”, and “Extreme Stable-Cut” are up.

Thus, let $z_{\text{Extreme Number}}$, $N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}$ and $G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}}$ be a Extreme number, a Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood and a Extreme Stable-Cut and the new terms are up.

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} &= \\
\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\
|N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} &= \\
\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} &= \\
\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\
|N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
= z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \mid \\
|N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} &= \\
\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
|N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} &= \\
\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
|N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

And with go back to initial structure,

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} = \\ &\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} | \\ &|N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ &= \max \{|E| | E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} &= \\ &\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\ &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} = \\ &\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} | \\ &|N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Extreme Number}} | \\ &|N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ &= \max \{|E| | E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} &= \\ &\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\ &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} | \\ &|N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ &= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \\ &= \max \{|E| | E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} G_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} &= \\ &\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\ &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} | \\ &|N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ &= \max \{|E| | E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices belong to any Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Cut if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Extreme SuperHyperVertex, some interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices are mutually Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors with no Extreme exception at all minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them.

To make sense with the precise words in the terms of “R-”, the follow-up illustrations are coming up.

The following Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperVertices is the simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme R-Stable-Cut.

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} | |E|=\max\{|E| | E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

The Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} | |E|=\max\{|E| | E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

Is the simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme R-Stable-Cut. The Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} | |E|=\max\{|E| | E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}}.$$

Is an **Extreme R-Stable-Cut** $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a Extreme type-SuperHyperSet with **the maximum Extreme cardinality** of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Extreme SuperHyperEdge amid some Extreme SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by **Extreme Stable-Cut** is related to the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

There's not only **one** Extreme SuperHyperVertex **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious Extreme Stable-Cut is up. The obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the Extreme Stable-Cut is a Extreme SuperHyperSet **includes** only **one** Extreme SuperHyperVertex. But the Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

doesn't have less than two SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet since they've come from at least so far an SuperHyperEdge. Thus the non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme R-Stable-Cut **is** up. To sum them up, the Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is the non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme R-Stable-Cut. Since the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$(V \setminus V \setminus \{x, z\}) \cup \{xy\}$$

or

$$(V \setminus V \setminus \{x, z\}) \cup \{zy\}$$

is an Extreme R-Stable-Cut $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Extreme SuperHyperEdge for some Extreme SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by that Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the Extreme Stable-Cut **and** it's an Extreme **Stable-Cut**. Since it's **the maximum Extreme cardinality** of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Extreme SuperHyperEdge for some amount Extreme SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by that Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the Extreme Stable-Cut. There isn't only less than two Extreme SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Thus the non-obvious Extreme R-Stable-Cut,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

is up. The non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme Stable-Cut, not:

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is the Extreme SuperHyperSet, not:

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

does includes only less than two SuperHyperVertices in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ but it's impossible in the case, they've corresponded to an SuperHyperEdge. It's interesting to mention that the only non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the

“Extreme R-Stable-Cut”

amid those obvious[non-obvious] simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSets called the

Extreme R-Stable-Cut,

is only and only

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

In a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling. It's also, not only a Extreme free-triangle embedded SuperHyperModel and a Extreme on-triangle embedded SuperHyperModel but also it's a Extreme stable embedded SuperHyperModel. But all only non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSets of the Extreme R-Stable-Cut amid those obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSets of the Extreme Stable-Cut, are

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

In a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$.

To sum them up, assume a connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then in the worst case, literally,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

is a Extreme R-Stable-Cut. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of a Extreme R-Stable-Cut is the cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

To sum them up, in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices belong to any Extreme quasi-R-Stable-Cut if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Extreme SuperHyperVertex, some interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices are mutually Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors with no Extreme exception at all minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them.

Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Let a Extreme SuperHyperEdge $ESHE : E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has some Extreme SuperHyperVertices r . Consider all Extreme numbers of those Extreme SuperHyperVertices from that Extreme SuperHyperEdge excluding excluding more than r distinct Extreme SuperHyperVertices, exclude to any given Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices. Consider there's a Extreme R-Stable-Cut with the least cardinality, the lower sharp Extreme bound for Extreme cardinality. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices $V_{ESHE} \setminus \{z\}$ is a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's a Extreme SuperHyperEdge to have some Extreme SuperHyperVertices uniquely but it isn't a Extreme R-Stable-Cut. Since it doesn't have **the maximum Extreme cardinality** of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's a Extreme SuperHyperEdge to have some SuperHyperVertices uniquely. The Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices $V_{ESHE} \cup \{z\}$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of a Extreme

SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices but it isn't a Extreme R-Stable-Cut. Since it **doesn't do** the Extreme procedure such that there's a Extreme SuperHyperEdge to have some Extreme SuperHyperVertices uniquely [there are at least one Extreme SuperHyperVertex outside implying there's, sometimes in the connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$, a Extreme SuperHyperVertex, titled its Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, to that Extreme SuperHyperVertex in the Extreme SuperHyperSet S so as S doesn't do "the Extreme procedure"]. There's only **one** Extreme SuperHyperVertex **outside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet, $V_{ESHE} \cup \{z\}$, in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood. Thus the obvious Extreme R-Stable-Cut, V_{ESHE} is up. The obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme R-Stable-Cut, V_{ESHE} , **is** a Extreme SuperHyperSet, V_{ESHE} , **includes** only **all** Extreme SuperHyperVertices does forms any kind of Extreme pairs are titled Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Since the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices V_{ESHE} , is the **maximum Extreme SuperHyperCardinality** of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices **such that** there's a Extreme SuperHyperEdge to have some Extreme SuperHyperVertices uniquely. Thus, in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Any Extreme R-Stable-Cut only contains all interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices and all exterior Extreme SuperHyperVertices from the unique Extreme SuperHyperEdge where there's any of them has all possible Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors in and there's all Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhoods in with no exception minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors to some of them not all of them but everything is possible about Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhoods and Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors out.

The SuperHyperNotion, namely, Stable-Cut, is up. There's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. The following Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] is the simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme Stable-Cut. The Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Cut} \\ &= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{ExtremeCardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{ExtremeCardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t. \end{aligned}$$

is the simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme Stable-Cut. The Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Cut} \\ &= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{ExtremeCardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{ExtremeCardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t. \end{aligned}$$

Is an **Extreme Stable-Cut** $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a Extreme type-SuperHyperSet with

the maximum Extreme cardinality of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] such that there's no Extreme SuperHyperVertex of a Extreme SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Extreme SuperHyperEdge for all Extreme SuperHyperVertices. There are not only **two** Extreme SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious Extreme Stable-Cut is up. The obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the Extreme Stable-Cut is a Extreme SuperHyperSet **includes** only **two** Extreme SuperHyperVertices. But the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Cut} \\ &= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t. \end{aligned}$$

Doesn't have less than three SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme Stable-Cut **is** up. To sum them up, the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Cut} \\ &= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t. \end{aligned}$$

Is the non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme Stable-Cut. Since the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Cut} \\ &= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t. \end{aligned}$$

Is an Extreme Stable-Cut $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's no a Extreme SuperHyperEdge for some Extreme SuperHyperVertices given by that Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the Extreme Stable-Cut **and** it's an Extreme **Stable-Cut**. Since it's **the maximum Extreme cardinality** of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] such that there's no Extreme SuperHyperVertex of a Extreme SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Extreme

SuperHyperEdge for all Extreme SuperHyperVertices. There aren't only less than three Extreme SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet, 1121
1122

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Cut} \\ &= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t. \end{aligned}$$

Thus the non-obvious Extreme Stable-Cut, 1123

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Cut} \\ &= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t. \end{aligned}$$

Is up. The obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme Stable-Cut, not: 1124

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Cut} \\ &= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t. \end{aligned}$$

Is the Extreme SuperHyperSet, not: 1125

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Cut} \\ &= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t. \end{aligned}$$

Does includes only less than three SuperHyperVertices in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. It's interesting to mention that the only non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the 1126
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1128

“Extreme Stable-Cut”

amid those obvious[non-obvious] simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSets called the 1129
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Extreme Stable-Cut,

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is only and only

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-Cut} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Stable-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

In a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. □

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5 The Extreme Departures on The Theoretical Results Toward Theoretical Motivations

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The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses.

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Proposition 5.1. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Stable-Cut} \\
&= \{E_{2i+1}{}_{2i+1=||ESHG||}\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Stable-Cut\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\frac{|ESHG|}{2}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ V-Stable-Cut} \\
&= \{V_{2i+1}{}_{2i+1=||ESHG||}^{INTERNAL}\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ V-Stable-Cut\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= az^{\frac{|ESHG|}{2}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& V_{\frac{|ESHG|}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{\frac{|ESHG|}{3}}
\end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
& E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\frac{|ESHG|}{3}}, V_{\frac{|ESHG|}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

Figure 23. a Extreme SuperHyperPath Associated to the Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Example (16.5)

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Cut. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 5.2. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperStable-Cut.

Proposition 5.3. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Stable-Cut} \\
 &= \{E_{2i+1} \mid 2i+1 = \lfloor |ENSHG| \rfloor\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Stable-Cut\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= 2z^{\frac{|ENSHG|}{2}}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ V-Stable-Cut} \\
 &= \{V_{2i+1}^{INTERNAL} \mid 2i+1 = \lfloor |ENSHG| \rfloor\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ V-Stable-Cut\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= az^{\frac{|ENSHG|}{2}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & V_{\frac{|ENSHG|}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{\frac{|ENSHG|}{3}}
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 24. a Extreme SuperHyperCycle Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.7)

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\lfloor \frac{ENSHG}{3} \rfloor}, V_{\lfloor \frac{ENSHG}{3} \rfloor}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Cut. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 5.4. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut.

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Proposition 5.5. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then 1161

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} \\
& = \{\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 0z^0. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{INTERNAL}}\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = az^{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{2}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 1162

$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
\text{CENTER}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
E_1, V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\
E_2, \text{CENTER}
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's 1164
a new way to redefine as 1165

$$\begin{aligned}
V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} & \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z & \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z. &
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is 1166
corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Cut. The latter is 1167
straightforward. $\square$ 1168

Example 5.6. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar 1169
 $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by 1170
the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the 1171
connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel 1172
(25), is the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1173

Proposition 5.7. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. 1174
Then 1175

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} \\
& = \{\text{MATCHING SuperHyperEdges}\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = az^{|\text{MATCHING SuperHyperEdges}|}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut}} \\
& = \{\text{One From Every MATCHING SuperHyperVertices}\} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 2bz^{|\text{One From Every MATCHING SuperHyperVertices}|}
\end{aligned}$$

Figure 25. a Extreme SuperHyperStar Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.9)

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 &E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}, V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Cut. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperStable-Cut. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperStable-Cut could

Figure 26. Extreme SuperHyperBipartite Extreme Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Example (16.11)

be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest SuperHyperStable-Cut taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 5.8. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut.

Proposition 5.9. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} \\
&= \{ \text{MATCHING SuperHyperEdges} \}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= a^z |\text{MATCHING SuperHyperEdges}|. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut}} \\
&= \{ \text{One From Every MATCHING SuperHyperVertices} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= 2bz |\text{One From Every MATCHING SuperHyperVertices}|
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

1198

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}.
\end{aligned}$$

1199

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& E_1, V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\
& E_2, V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}, V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperStable-Cut taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Cut. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperStable-Cut. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperStable-Cut could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

Figure 27. a Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Example (16.13)

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 5.10. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut.

Proposition 5.11. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{E_{2i+1} \mid 2i+1 = \lfloor |E_{NSHG}| \rfloor\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 2z^{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{2}}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut}} \\
 &= \{V_{2i+1}^{INTERNAL} \mid 2i+1 = \lfloor |E_{NSHG}| \rfloor\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Stable-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= az^{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{2}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\
 & CENTER, E_2^*
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 & E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
 & E_2^*, CENTER
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 28. a Extreme SuperHyperWheel Extreme Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.15)

is a longest SuperHyperStable-Cut taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperStable-Cut. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperStable-Cut. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperStable-Cut could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperStable-Cut proposes some longest SuperHyperStable-Cut excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 5.12. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut.

6 The Surveys of Mathematical Sets On The Results But As The Initial Motivation

For the SuperHyperStable-Cut, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut, and the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut, some general results are introduced.

Remark 6.1. Let remind that the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut is “redefined” on the positions of the alphabets.

Corollary 6.2. *Assume Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut. Then*

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Extreme SuperHyperStable - Cut} = \\ & \{ \text{the SuperHyperStable - Cut of the SuperHyperVertices} \mid \\ & \max | \text{SuperHyperOffensive} \\ & \text{SuperHyperStable - Cut} \\ & | \text{Extremecardinalityamidthose SuperHyperStable - Cut.} \} \end{aligned}$$

plus one Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor to one. Where σ_i is the unary operation on the SuperHyperVertices of the SuperHyperGraph to assign the determinacy, the indeterminacy and the neutrality, for $i = 1, 2, 3$, respectively.

Corollary 6.3. *Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then the notion of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut and SuperHyperStable-Cut coincide.*

Corollary 6.4. *Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then a consecutive sequence of the SuperHyperVertices is a Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut if and only if it's a SuperHyperStable-Cut.*

Corollary 6.5. *Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then a consecutive sequence of the SuperHyperVertices is a strongest SuperHyperStable-Cut if and only if it's a longest SuperHyperStable-Cut.*

Corollary 6.6. *Assume SuperHyperClasses of a Extreme SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then its Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut is its SuperHyperStable-Cut and reversely.*

Corollary 6.7. *Assume a Extreme SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStable-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel) on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then its Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut is its SuperHyperStable-Cut and reversely.*

Corollary 6.8. *Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then its Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut isn't well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperStable-Cut isn't well-defined.*

Corollary 6.9. *Assume SuperHyperClasses of a Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then its Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut isn't well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperStable-Cut isn't well-defined.*

Corollary 6.10. *Assume a Extreme SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStable-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). Then its Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut isn't well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperStable-Cut isn't well-defined.*

Corollary 6.11. *Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then its Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut is well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperStable-Cut is well-defined.*

Corollary 6.12. *Assume SuperHyperClasses of a Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then its Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut is well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperStable-Cut is well-defined.*

Corollary 6.13. *Assume a Extreme SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStable-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). Then its Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut is well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperStable-Cut is well-defined.*

Proposition 6.14. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then V is* 1282

(i) : *the dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1283

(ii) : *the strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1284

(iii) : *the connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1285

(iv) : *the δ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1286

(v) : *the strong δ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1287

(vi) : *the connected δ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut.* 1288

Proposition 6.15. *Let $NTG : (V, E, \sigma, \mu)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then $\emptyset$ is* 1289

(i) : *the SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1290

(ii) : *the strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1291

(iii) : *the connected defensive SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1292

(iv) : *the δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1293

(v) : *the strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1294

(vi) : *the connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut.* 1295

Proposition 6.16. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then an independent SuperHyperSet is* 1296

(i) : *the SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1298

(ii) : *the strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1299

(iii) : *the connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1300

(iv) : *the δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1301

(v) : *the strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1302

(vi) : *the connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut.* 1303

Proposition 6.17. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStable-Cut/SuperHyperPath. Then V is a maximal* 1304

(i) : *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1307

(ii) : *strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1308

(iii) : *connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1309

(iv) : *$\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1310

(v) : *strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1311

(vi) : *connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut;* 1312

Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1313

Proposition 6.18. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperWheel. Then V is a maximal* 1314

1315

(i) : dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1316

(ii) : strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1317

(iii) : connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1318

(iv) : $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1319

(v) : strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1320

(vi) : connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1321

Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1322

Proposition 6.19. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStable-Cut/SuperHyperPath. Then the number of 1323
of 1324
of 1325

(i) : the SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1326

(ii) : the SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1327

(iii) : the connected SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1328

(iv) : the $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1329

(v) : the strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1330

(vi) : the connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1331

is one and it's only V . Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1332
1333

Proposition 6.20. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperWheel. Then the number of 1334
of 1335

(i) : the dual SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1336

(ii) : the dual SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1337

(iii) : the dual connected SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1338

(iv) : the dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1339

(v) : the strong dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1340

(vi) : the connected dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1341

is one and it's only V . Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1342
1343

Proposition 6.21. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then a SuperHyperSet contains [the SuperHyperCenter and] the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices is a 1344
1345
1346
1347
1348

(i) : dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1349

(ii) : strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1350

(iii) : connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1351

(iv) : $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1352

(v) : strong $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1353

(vi) : connected $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1354

Proposition 6.22. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then a SuperHyperSet contains the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices in the biggest SuperHyperPart is a 1355
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(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1361

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1362

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1363

(iv) : δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1364

(v) : strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1365

(vi) : connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1366

Proposition 6.23. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then Then the number of 1367
1368
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(i) : dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1371

(ii) : strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1372

(iii) : connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1373

(iv) : $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1374

(v) : strong $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1375

(vi) : connected $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1376

is one and it's only S , a SuperHyperSet contains [the SuperHyperCenter and] the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices. Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1377
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Proposition 6.24. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph. The number of connected component is $|V - S|$ if there's a SuperHyperSet which is a dual 1381
1382

(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1383

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1384

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1385

(iv) : SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1386

(v) : strong 1-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1387

(vi) : connected 1-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1388

Proposition 6.25. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then the number is at most $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ and the Extreme number is at most $\mathcal{O}_n(ESHG)$.* 1389
1390

Proposition 6.26. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperComplete. The number is $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1$ and the Extreme number is $\min \sum_{v \in \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_t\}_{t > \frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2}} \subseteq V} \sigma(v)$, in the setting of dual* 1391
1392
1393

(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1394

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1395

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1396

(iv) : $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1397

(v) : strong $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1398

(vi) : connected $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1399

Proposition 6.27. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is $\emptyset$. The number is 0 and the Extreme number is 0, for an independent SuperHyperSet in the setting of dual* 1400
1401
1402

(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1403

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1404

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1405

(iv) : 0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1406

(v) : strong 0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1407

(vi) : connected 0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1408

Proposition 6.28. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperComplete. Then there's no independent SuperHyperSet.* 1409
1410

Proposition 6.29. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperStable-Cut/SuperHyperPath/SuperHyperWheel. The number is $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ and the Extreme number is $\mathcal{O}_n(ESHG : (V, E))$, in the setting of a dual* 1411
1412
1413
1414

(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1415

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1416

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1417

(iv) : $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1418

(v) : strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1419

(vi) : connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1420

Proposition 6.30. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperStar/complete SuperHyperBipartite/complete SuperHyperMultiPartite. The number is $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1$ and the Extreme number is $\min \sum_{v \in \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_t\}_{t > \frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2}} \subseteq V} \sigma(v)$, in the setting of a dual* 1421
1422
1423
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(i) : *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut*; 1425

(ii) : *strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut*; 1426

(iii) : *connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut*; 1427

(iv) : $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -*SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut*; 1428

(v) : *strong* $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -*SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut*; 1429

(vi) : *connected* $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -*SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut*. 1430

Proposition 6.31. *Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be a SuperHyperFamily of the ESHGs : (V, E) Extreme SuperHyperGraphs which are from one-type SuperHyperClass which the result is obtained for the individuals. Then the results also hold for the SuperHyperFamily $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ of these specific SuperHyperClasses of the Extreme SuperHyperGraphs.* 1431
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Proposition 6.32. *Let ESHG : (V, E) be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph. If S is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut, then $\forall v \in V \setminus S, \exists x \in S$ such that* 1435
1436

(i) $v \in N_s(x)$; 1437

(ii) $vx \in E$. 1438

Proposition 6.33. *Let ESHG : (V, E) be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph. If S is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut, then* 1439
1440

(i) S is SuperHyperStable-Cut set; 1441

(ii) there's $S \subseteq S'$ such that $|S'|$ is SuperHyperChromatic number. 1442

Proposition 6.34. *Let ESHG : (V, E) be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then* 1443

(i) $\Gamma \leq \mathcal{O}$; 1444

(ii) $\Gamma_s \leq \mathcal{O}_n$. 1445

Proposition 6.35. *Let ESHG : (V, E) be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is connected. Then* 1446
1447

(i) $\Gamma \leq \mathcal{O} - 1$; 1448

(ii) $\Gamma_s \leq \mathcal{O}_n - \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(x)$. 1449

Proposition 6.36. *Let ESHG : (V, E) be an odd SuperHyperPath. Then* 1450

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1451
1452

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ and corresponded SuperHyperSet is $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$; 1453

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}$; 1454

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only a dual SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1455
1456

Proposition 6.37. *Let ESHG : (V, E) be an even SuperHyperPath. Then* 1457

(i) the set $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1458

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ and corresponded SuperHyperSets are $\{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $\{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$; 1459
1460

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\};$ 1461

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1462
1463

Proposition 6.38. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an even SuperHyperStable-Cut. Then 1464

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1465
1466

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ and corresponded SuperHyperSets are $\{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $\{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\};$ 1467
1468

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}} \sigma(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sigma(s)\};$ 1469

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1470
1471

Proposition 6.39. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an odd SuperHyperStable-Cut. Then 1472

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1473
1474

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ and corresponded SuperHyperSet is $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\};$ 1475

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\};$ 1476

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1477
1478

Proposition 6.40. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be SuperHyperStar. Then 1479

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{c\}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1480

(ii) $\Gamma = 1;$ 1481

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(c);$ 1482

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{c\}$ and $S \subset S'$ are only dual SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1483

Proposition 6.41. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be SuperHyperWheel. Then 1484

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1485
1486

(ii) $\Gamma = |\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}|;$ 1487

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \sum_{\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s);$ 1488

(iv) the SuperHyperSet $\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9 \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}$ is only a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1489
1490

Proposition 6.42. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an odd SuperHyperComplete. Then 1491

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1492
1493

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1;$ 1494

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}};$ 1495

(iv) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is only a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1496
1497

Proposition 6.43. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an even SuperHyperComplete. Then 1498

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1499
1500

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$; 1501

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}}$; 1502

(iv) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is only a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1503
1504

Proposition 6.44. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be a m -SuperHyperFamily of Extreme SuperHyperStars with common Extreme SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then 1505
1506

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut for $\mathcal{NSHF}$; 1507
1508

(ii) $\Gamma = m$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1509

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^3 \sigma_j(c_i)$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1510

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m\}$ and $S \subset S'$ are only dual SuperHyperStable-Cut for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$. 1511
1512

Proposition 6.45. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be an m -SuperHyperFamily of odd SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperGraphs with common Extreme SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then 1513
1514
1515

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut for $\mathcal{NSHF}$; 1516
1517

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1518

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}}$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1519

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ are only a dual maximal SuperHyperStable-Cut for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$. 1520
1521

Proposition 6.46. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be a m -SuperHyperFamily of even SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperGraphs with common Extreme SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then 1522
1523
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(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1525
1526

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1527

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}}$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1528

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ are only dual maximal SuperHyperStable-Cut for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$. 1529
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Proposition 6.47. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1531
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(i) if $s \geq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is an t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut, then S is an s -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1533
1534
1535

(ii) if $s \leq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is a dual t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut, then S is a dual s -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1536
1537
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Proposition 6.48. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1539
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(i) if $s \geq t + 2$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is an t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut, then S is an s -SuperHyperPowerful SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1541
1542
1543

(ii) if $s \leq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is a dual t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut, then S is a dual s -SuperHyperPowerful SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1544
1545
1546

Proposition 6.49. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a $[an]$ $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1547
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(i) if $\forall a \in S$, $|N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1550
1551

(ii) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S$, $|N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1552
1553

(iii) if $\forall a \in S$, $|N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an V -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1554
1555

(iv) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S$, $|N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual V -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1556
1557

Proposition 6.50. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a $[an]$ $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1558
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(i) $\forall a \in S$, $|N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1561
1562

(ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S$, $|N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1563
1564

(iii) $\forall a \in S$, $|N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an V -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1565
1566

(iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S$, $|N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual V -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1567
1568

Proposition 6.51. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a $[an]$ $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperComplete. Then following statements hold; 1569
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1571

(i) $\forall a \in S$, $|N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{O-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1572
1573

(ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S$, $|N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{O-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1574
1575

(iii) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1576
1577

(iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1578
1579

Proposition 6.52. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperComplete. Then following statements hold; 1580
1581
1582

(i) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1583
1584

(ii) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1585
1586

(iii) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1587
1588

(iv) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1589
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Proposition 6.53. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperStable-Cut. Then following statements hold; 1591
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1593

(i) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < 2$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1594
1595

(ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > 2$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1596
1597

(iii) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1598
1599

(iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1600
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Proposition 6.54. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperStable-Cut. Then following statements hold; 1602
1603
1604

(i) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < 2$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1605
1606

(ii) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > 2$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1607
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(iii) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut; 1609
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(iv) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1611
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7 Extreme Applications in Cancer's Extreme Recognition

The cancer is the Extreme disease but the Extreme model is going to figure out what's going on this Extreme phenomenon. The special Extreme case of this Extreme disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The Extreme recognition of the cancer could help to find some Extreme treatments for this Extreme disease.

In the following, some Extreme steps are Extreme devised on this disease.

Step 1. (Extreme Definition) The Extreme recognition of the cancer in the long-term Extreme function.

Step 2. (Extreme Issue) The specific region has been assigned by the Extreme model [it's called Extreme SuperHyperGraph] and the long Extreme cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Extreme SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done.

Step 3. (Extreme Model) There are some specific Extreme models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some general Extreme models. The moves and the Extreme traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Extreme SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStable-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut or the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut in those Extreme Extreme SuperHyperModels.

8 Case 1: The Initial Extreme Steps Toward Extreme SuperHyperBipartite as Extreme SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Extreme Solution) In the Extreme Figure (29), the Extreme SuperHyperBipartite is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. By using the Extreme Figure (29) and the Table (4), the Extreme SuperHyperBipartite is obtained. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (29), is the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut.

9 Case 2: The Increasing Extreme Steps Toward Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite as Extreme SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Extreme Solution) In the Extreme Figure (30), the Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured.

Figure 29. a Extreme SuperHyperBipartite Associated to the Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut

Table 4. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyper-Edges Belong to The Extreme SuperHyperBipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Figure 30. a Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut

Table 5. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

By using the Extreme Figure (30) and the Table (5), the Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite is obtained. 1655

The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (30), is the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut. 1656
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10 Wondering Open Problems But As The Directions To Forming The Motivations 1661

In what follows, some “problems” and some “questions” are proposed. 1663

The SuperHyperStable-Cut and the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut are defined on a real-world application, titled “Cancer’s Recognitions”. 1664
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Question 10.1. Which the else SuperHyperModels could be defined based on Cancer’s recognitions? 1666
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Question 10.2. Are there some SuperHyperNotions related to SuperHyperStable-Cut and the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut? 1668
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Question 10.3. Are there some Algorithms to be defined on the SuperHyperModels to compute them? 1670
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Question 10.4. Which the SuperHyperNotions are related to beyond the SuperHyperStable-Cut and the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut? 1672
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Problem 10.5. The SuperHyperStable-Cut and the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut do a SuperHyperModel for the Cancer’s recognitions and they’re based on SuperHyperStable-Cut, are there else? 1674
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Problem 10.6. Which the fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are related to these SuperHyperNumbers types-results? 1677
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Problem 10.7. What’s the independent research based on Cancer’s recognitions concerning the multiple types of SuperHyperNotions? 1679
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11 Conclusion and Closing Remarks 1681

In this section, concluding remarks and closing remarks are represented. The drawbacks of this research are illustrated. Some benefits and some advantages of this research are highlighted. 1682
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This research uses some approaches to make Extreme SuperHyperGraphs more understandable. In this endeavor, two SuperHyperNotions are defined on the SuperHyperStable-Cut. For that sake in the second definition, the main definition of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph is redefined on the position of the alphabets. Based on the 1685
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new definition for the Extreme SuperHyperGraph, the new SuperHyperNotion, Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut, finds the convenient background to implement some results based on that. Some SuperHyperClasses and some Extreme SuperHyperClasses are the cases of this research on the modeling of the regions where are under the attacks of the cancer to recognize this disease as it's mentioned on the title "Cancer's Recognitions". To formalize the instances on the SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperStable-Cut, the new SuperHyperClasses and SuperHyperClasses, are introduced. Some general results are gathered in the section on the SuperHyperStable-Cut and the Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut. The clarifications, instances and literature reviews have taken the whole way through. In this research, the literature reviews have fulfilled the lines containing the notions and the results. The SuperHyperGraph and Extreme SuperHyperGraph are the SuperHyperModels on the "Cancer's Recognitions" and both bases are the background of this research. Sometimes the cancer has been happened on the region, full of cells, groups of cells and embedded styles. In this segment, the SuperHyperModel proposes some SuperHyperNotions based on the connectivities of the moves of the cancer in the longest and strongest styles with the formation of the design and the architecture are formally called " SuperHyperStable-Cut" in the themes of jargons and buzzwords. The prefix "SuperHyper" refers to the theme of the embedded styles to figure out the background for the SuperHyperNotions. In the Table (6),

Table 6. An Overlook On This Research And Beyond

Advantages	Limitations
1. Redefining Extreme SuperHyperGraph	1. General Results
2. SuperHyperStable-Cut	
3. Extreme SuperHyperStable-Cut	2. Other SuperHyperNumbers
4. Modeling of Cancer's Recognitions	
5. SuperHyperClasses	3. SuperHyperFamilies

benefits and avenues for this research are, figured out, pointed out and spoken out.

12 Extreme SuperHyperDuality But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 12.1. (Different Extreme Types of Extreme SuperHyperDuality).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall E_i \in E', \exists E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E'$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall E_i \in E', \exists E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E'$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$ and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall V_i \in V', \exists V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V'$ such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;

(iv) **Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall V_i \in V', \exists V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V'$ such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$ and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$; 1723
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(v) **Extreme SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality. 1726
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Definition 12.2. ((Extreme) SuperHyperDuality). 1729

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called 1730
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(i) an **Extreme SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; 1732
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(ii) a **Extreme SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; 1740
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(iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 1747
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(iv) a **Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 1757
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(v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality 1767
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of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; 1771-1774

(vi) a **Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; 1775-1781

(vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 1782-1791

(viii) a **Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient. 1792-1801

Example 12.3. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items. 1802-1803

- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperDuality. 1804-1811

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1812-1813

E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperDuality.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_4, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 15z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, E_{3i+24_{i=0}^3}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 6z^8. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_{3i+1_{i=0}^7}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 6z^8.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1830
1831

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1832
1833

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, E_{23}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, V_{15}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1834
1835

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1836
1837

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1, E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_6, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1838
1839

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_{i=4}^{i \neq 5, 7, 8}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1840
1841

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_5, E_9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1842
1843

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1844
1845

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1846
1847

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(2 \times 1 \times 2) + (2 \times 4 \times 5)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1848
1849

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(1 \times 1 \times 2)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1850
1851

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(2 \times 2 \times 2)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1852
1853

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0^3}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0^5}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1854
1855

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1856
1857

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1858
1859

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10 \times 9 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 9 + 12 \times 6z^2.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses. 1860
1861

Proposition 12.4. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then 1862
1863

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}.\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 1864

$$\begin{aligned}P : \\ V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}.\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.6. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperDuality} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &= 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperDuality} &= \\ &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &= \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}, E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.8. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} |z|. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.10. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_i \in E_{P_i, ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\ & \quad z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, i \neq j\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is
straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi
isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied.
There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one
SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL} \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite
 $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only
minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL} \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □ 1911

Example 12.11. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme
SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured.
The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme
result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme
SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the
Extreme SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.12. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite 1918

$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extremal\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality} \\
&= \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extremal\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose } |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
& \quad z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extremal\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality} \\
&= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, i \neq j\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extremal\ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Extremal\ Cardinality}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only

minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution 1931

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite 1932
 $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$ 1933

Example 12.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite 1934
 $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme 1935
SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme 1936
SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, 1937
in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperDuality. 1938

Proposition 12.14. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. 1939
Then, 1940

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i | E_i^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Extreme \text{ Cardinality}} |z|. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 1941

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2^*, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Extreme \text{ Cardinality}}, V_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Extreme \text{ Cardinality}}+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel 1942
 $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 1943

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\
 \exists! E_z^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z^* \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z^*.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term ‘EXTERNAL’ implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is 1944
corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is 1945
straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi 1946
isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied. 1947
The unique embedded SuperHyperDuality proposes some longest SuperHyperDuality 1948
excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$ 1949

Example 12.15. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme 1950
SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained 1951
Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme 1952
SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in 1953
the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperDuality. 1954

13 Extreme SuperHyperJoin But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 13.1. (Different Extreme Types of Extreme SuperHyperJoin).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$;
- (iv) **Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Extreme SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin.

Definition 13.2. ((Extreme) SuperHyperJoin).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin;
- (ii) a **Extreme SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin;
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

- (iv) a **Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
 Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme
 v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme
 SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial
 contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum
 Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of a Extreme
 SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme
 SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the
 Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme
 coefficient; 2001-2010
- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin,
 Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme
 rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph
 $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme
 SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
 in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme
 SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; 2011-2017
- (vi) a **Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin,
 Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme
 rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph
 $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme
 SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality
 consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such
 that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; 2018-2024
- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
 Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme
 v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
 of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme
 SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the
 Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme
 coefficient; 2025-2034
- (viii) a **Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
 Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme
 v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme
 SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial
 contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum
 Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme
 SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme
 SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the
 Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme
 coefficient. 2035-2044

Example 13.3. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$
 in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items. 2045-2046

- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
 SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1
 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme 2047-2049

SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of
 Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely,
 E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no
 Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme
 SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_2, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
 SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.
 E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Extreme
 SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's
 only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex,
 V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a
 Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every
 given Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_2, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
 SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_2, V_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
 SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
 SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2069
2070

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{3i+24^3_{i=0}}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_{3i+1^7_{i=0}}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2071
2072

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2073
2074

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.$$

- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2075
2076

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{23}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^5.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, V_{15}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^5.$$

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2077
2078

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2079
2080

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_1, E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_6, V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2081
2082

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_{i=4}^{i \neq 5,7,8}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 5z^5.$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2083
2084

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_3, E_9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_6\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2085
2086

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2087
2088

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_2, E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2089
2090

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_2, E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = (1 \times 5 \times 5) + (1 \times 2 + 1)z^3.$$

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2091
2092

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_2, E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.$$

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2093
2094

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2095
2096

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0^3}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0^5}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2097
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2099
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2101
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= 10 \times 6 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 6 + 12 \times 6z^2.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses. 2103
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Proposition 13.4. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. 2105

Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \\
& = \frac{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}{\{E_i\}_{i=1}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z \frac{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}{\{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
& = \frac{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}{\{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \frac{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}{\mathcal{Z}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}.
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is
straightforward. $\square$

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Example 13.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath
 $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the
Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperJoin.

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Proposition 13.6. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$.
Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \\
& = \frac{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}{\{E_i\}_{i=1}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z \frac{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}{\{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
& = \frac{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}{\{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \frac{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}{\mathcal{Z}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}, V^{EXTERNAL} \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 13.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHG : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

Proposition 13.8. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}|z. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 13.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

Proposition 13.10. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\ &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ & \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\ &= (\text{OTHERWISE}). \end{aligned}$$

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$$\text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|.$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \end{aligned}$$

$$= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose } |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right)$$

$$z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= (\text{OTHERWISE})0. \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}}$$

$$= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, i \neq j\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} & P : \\ & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ & \dots, \\ & E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL} \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied.

There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 13.11. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

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Proposition 13.12. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\ = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$\{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\ = (\text{OTHERWISE}).$$

$\{\}$,

$$\text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose } |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\ z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}$$

$$\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = (\text{OTHERWISE})0.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\ = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, i \neq j\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one

SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only

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minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 13.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

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Proposition 13.14. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperJoin} = \\
 &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperJoin\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperJoin} \\
 &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperJoin\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= \prod |V^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}.
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperJoin proposes some longest SuperHyperJoin excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 13.15. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

14 Extreme SuperHyperPerfect But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 14.1. (Different Extreme Types of Extreme SuperHyperPerfect).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;
- (iv) **Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect.

Definition 14.2. ((Extreme) SuperHyperPerfect).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph

- $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; 2224-2227
- (ii) a **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; 2228-2234
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 2235-2244
- (iv) a **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 2245-2254
- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; 2255-2262
- (vi) a **Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; 2263-2269
- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an 2270-2272

Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

- (viii) a **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient.

Example 14.3. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items.

- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme

SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2309

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2310 2311

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2312 2313

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2314 2315

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_{3i+1}_{i=0}^3, E_{3i+24}_{i=0}^3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_{3i+1}_{i=0}^7\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2316 2317

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2318 2319

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2320
2321

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, E_{23}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, V_{15}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2322
2323

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2324
2325

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_1, E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_6, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 2z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2326
2327

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1, V_{i=4}^{i \neq 5,7,8}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2328
2329

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_3, E_9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2330
2331

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2332
2333

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2334
2335

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 5 \times 5) + (1 \times 2 + 1)z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2336
2337

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2338
2339

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2340
2341

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0^3}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0^5}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2342
2343

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2344
2345

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2346
2347

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10 \times 6 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 6 + 12 \times 6z^2. \end{aligned}$$

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses. 2348
2349

Proposition 14.4. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then 2350
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \prod |V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2352

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}. \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2353
2354

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. 2355
2356
□ 2357

Example 14.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperPerfect. 2358
2359
2360

Proposition 14.6. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. Then 2361
2362

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2363

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}.
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2364
2365

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. 2366
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Example 14.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect. 2369
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Proposition 14.8. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then 2372
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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = |i | E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} | z. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 14.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

Proposition 14.10. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect} \\ &= (PERFECT\ MATCHING). \\ &\{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ &\quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect} \\ &= (OTHERWISE). \\ &\{\}, \\ &If\ \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= (PERFECT\ MATCHING). \\ &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) choose |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\ &\quad z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ &where\ \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= (OTHERWISE)0. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect} \\ &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| choose 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 14.11. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

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Proposition 14.12. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\ = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$\{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\ = (\text{OTHERWISE}).$$

$\{\}$,

$$\text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose } |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\ z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}$$

$$\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = (\text{OTHERWISE})0.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\ = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, i \neq j\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}}$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have

one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only

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minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 14.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme

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SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme

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SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$,

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in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

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Proposition 14.14. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$.

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Then,

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperPerfect} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} |z. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperPerfect} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel

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$ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is

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corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is

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straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi

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isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be applied. The

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unique embedded SuperHyperPerfect proposes some longest SuperHyperPerfect excerpt

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from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 14.15. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

15 Extreme SuperHyperTotal But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 15.1. (Different Extreme Types of Extreme SuperHyperTotal).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;
- (iv) **Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Extreme SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal.

Definition 15.2. ((Extreme) SuperHyperTotal).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;
- (ii) a **Extreme SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;

- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
 Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme
 v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of
 an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme
 SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the
 Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme
 coefficient;

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- (iv) a **Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
 Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme
 v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of
 a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme
 SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the
 Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme
 coefficient;

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- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal,
 Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme
 rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph
 $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme
 SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
 in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme
 SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;

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- (vi) a **Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal,
 Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme
 rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph
 $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme
 SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality
 consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such
 that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;

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- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
 Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme
 v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
 of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme
 SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the
 Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme
 coefficient;

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- (viii) a **Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
 Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme
 v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices

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of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient.

Example 15.3. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items.

- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperTotal.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperTotal.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-}} = \{E_4, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2556
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2558
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 20z^{10}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 20z^{10}.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2560
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_{12}, E_{13}, E_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2562
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2564
2565

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 10z^{10}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 20z^{10}.$$

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2566
2567

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2568
2569

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_6, E_7, E_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2570
2571

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_{i=1}^{i \neq 4,5,6}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2572
2573

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_3, E_9, E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2574
2575

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2576
2577

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_2, V_3, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2578
2579

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2580
2581

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2582
2583

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2 \times 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2584
2585

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{i+2_{i=011}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{i+2_{i=011}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2586
2587

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_6, E_{10}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 9z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (|V| - 1)z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2588
2589

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 9z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2590
2591

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_3, V_{10}, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 6z^3.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses. 2592
2593

Proposition 15.4. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then 2594
2595

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
& = z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperTotal} \\
& = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
& = \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2596

$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\
\dots
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2597
2598

$$\begin{aligned}
V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} & \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} & \in E_z \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} & \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. 2599
2600
2601

Example 15.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperTotal. 2602
2603
2604

Proposition 15.6. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. Then 2605
2606

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
& = (|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} - 1) \\
& z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperTotal} \\
& = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
& = \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\
 \dots, \\
 \frac{E^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 1} V^{EXTERNAL}}{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 1}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.8. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_i, E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i(i-1)| E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} |z^2|. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{CENTER, V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 &(|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}) \text{ choose } (|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 1) \\
 &z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.10. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ & \quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z \min_{|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} \\ &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 15.11. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the Extreme SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.12. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal} \\
 &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i ESHG:(V,E)}, \\
 & \quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
 & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\
 &= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal} \\
 &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{ choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only

minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution 2663

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite 2664
 $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □ 2665

Example 15.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite 2666
 $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme 2667
 SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme 2668
 SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, 2669
 in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperTotal. 2670

Proposition 15.14. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. 2671
 Then, 2672

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \{E_i, E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= |i(i-1) \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperTotal} &= \{CENTER, V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &(|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}) \text{ choose } (|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} - 1) \\ &z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2673

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, CENTER, E_j.$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel 2674
 $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2675

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is 2676
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is 2677
 straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi 2678
 isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. The 2679
 unique embedded SuperHyperTotal proposes some longest SuperHyperTotal excerpt 2680
 from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. □ 2681

Example 15.15. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme 2682
 SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained 2683
 Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme 2684
 SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in 2685
 the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperTotal. 2686

16 Extreme SuperHyperConnected But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 16.1. (Different Extreme Types of Extreme SuperHyperConnected).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$;
- (iv) **Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Extreme SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected.

Definition 16.2. ((Extreme) SuperHyperConnected).

Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Extreme SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected;
- (ii) a **Extreme SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected;
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme

SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

- (iv) a **Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;
- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the consecutive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected;
- (vi) a **Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected;
- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;
- (viii) a **Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of a Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality consecutive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient.

Example 16.3. Assume a Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items.

- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperConnected. 2782
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as a Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperConnected. 2791
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2799
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2802
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_1, E_2, E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely 2805
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straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 20z^{10}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 20z^{10}.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_{12}, E_{13}, E_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 10z^{10}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_{i+1}_{i=11}^9, V_{22}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 20z^{10}.$$

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely

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straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_1, E_6, E_7, E_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1, V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1, V_{i=1}^{i \neq 4,5,6}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_3, E_9, E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1, V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_2, V_3, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2838
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2841
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2844
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2 \times 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2847
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{i+2_{i=011}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{i+2_{i=011}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2850
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2853
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 10z.$$

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2856
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_3, E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_3, V_{10}, V_6\}.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = 3 \times 6z^3. \end{aligned}$$

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses. 2859
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Proposition 16.4. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then 2861
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} =$$

$$= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} =$$

$$= z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} =$$

$$= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} =$$

$$= \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}$$

Proof. Let 2863

$P :$

$V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2,$

$V_3^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_3,$

$\dots,$

$E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 1}, V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 1}.$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2864
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$$V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv$$

$$\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv$$

$$\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 16.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHPP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.6. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHCC : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected} = \\ & = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ & = (|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 1) \\ & \quad z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected} \\ & = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ & = \prod |V^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 2} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} & P : \\ & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ & V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\ & \dots, \\ & E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 1}, V^{EXTERNAL}_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 1}. \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHCC : (V, E)$. There’s a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 16.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.8. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ SuperHyperConnected} = \{E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ & = |i \mid E_i \in |E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} z. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ R-SuperHyperConnected} = \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ R-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} = z. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.10. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ &\quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= \underset{z}{\min} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ V-SuperHyperConnected} \\ &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ V-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{ choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s no at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 16.11. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the Extreme SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.12. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ & \quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z_{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ V-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ V-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Extreme \text{ Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{ choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 16.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.14. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperConnected} &= \{E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= |i \mid E_i \in |E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}|z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ V-SuperHyperConnected} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ V-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V^{EXTERNAL}_i, E^*_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi isn’t up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperConnected proposes some longest SuperHyperConnected excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.15. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperConnected.

17 Background

There are some scientific researches covering the topic of this research. In what follows, there are some discussion and literature reviews about them date back on March 09, 2023.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “neutrosophic co-degree and neutrosophic degree alongside chromatic numbers in the setting of some classes related to neutrosophic hypergraphs” in **Ref. [1]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms without using neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Current Trends in Computer Science Research (JCTCSR)” with ISO abbreviation “J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res” in volume 1 and issue 1 with pages 06-14. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes” in **Ref. [2]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)” with ISO abbreviation “J Math Techniques Comput Math” in volume 1 and issue 3 with pages 242-263. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments” in **Ref. [76]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer’s Treatments. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)” with ISO abbreviation “J Math Techniques Comput Math” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 35-47. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

In some articles are titled “0039 — Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph” in **Ref. [4]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “0049 — (Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs” in **Ref. [5]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [6]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition” in **Ref. [7]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [8]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” in **Ref. [9]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [10]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [11]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [12]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [13]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [14]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond” in **Ref. [15]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs ” in **Ref. [16]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [12]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [17]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [18]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances” in **Ref. [19]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses” in **Ref. [20]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions” in **Ref. [21]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments” in **Ref. [22]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses” in **Ref. [23]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperMatching By (R-)Definitions And Polynomials To Monitor Cancer’s Recognition In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [90]** by Henry

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Some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [121]** by Henry Garrett (2022) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 3230 readers in Scribd. It’s titled “Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs” and published by Ohio: E-publishing: Educational Publisher 1091 West 1st Ave Grandview Heights, Ohio 43212 United State. This research book covers different types of notions and settings in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory.

Also, some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [122]** by Henry Garrett (2022) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 4117 readers in Scribd. It’s titled “Neutrosophic Duality” and published by Florida: GLOBAL KNOWLEDGE - Publishing House 848 Brickell Ave Ste 950 Miami, Florida 33131 United States. This research book presents different types of notions SuperHyperResolving and SuperHyperDominating in the setting of duality in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory. This research book has scrutiny on the complement of the intended set and the intended set,

simultaneously. It's smart to consider a set but acting on its complement that what's done in this research book which is popular in the terms of high readers in Scribd.

See the seminal scientific researches [1,2]. The formalization of the notions on the framework of notions In SuperHyperGraphs, Neutrosophic notions In SuperHyperGraphs theory, and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs theory at [4-44,46-120]. Two popular scientific research books in Scribd in the terms of high readers, 3230 and 4117 respectively, on neutrosophic science is on [121,122].

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